

Understanding, Facilitating, and Connecting AI and Data Science Futures in Sub- Saharan Africa's Public Sector

Stakeholder Consultation Report

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This document summarises the third strategic consultation of the **Data for Policy SSA Engagement Programme**, held on 8 July, 2024 at Imperial College London. The workshop deepened DfP's engagement with SSA by presenting its theory of change and consortium framework, facilitating knowledge sharing, and fostering collaborative, forward-looking discussions.

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Understanding, Facilitating, and Connecting AI and Data Science Futures in Sub-Saharan Africa's Public Sector

8 July 2024 | Data Science Institute Boardroom, Imperial College London

1. Introduction

Over the past 18 months, Data for Policy CIC (DfP) has examined and worked on ways to address the underrepresentation of Sub-Saharan African (SSA) researchers and practitioners within its network and the global research to policy and public service delivery dialogue. Through a series of initiatives and collaborative efforts supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, DfP has engaged with and brought together diverse stakeholders to emphasise local and regional successes and challenge binding constraints to SSA knowledge and research generation, platforms, integration of data science and AI in public sector decision making and service delivery, grassroots engagement, and evidence impact at nexus of data and policy.

The work began with a desk review of data science and AI research and its use in policy and public service delivery and a structured review of SSA representation within current data and policy publishing landscape. Next, DfP engaged global actors working within SSA data science, AI research and policymaking with key informant interviews on SSA's data for policy operational and publishing ecosystems and data science and AI influence on and usage in policy making and service delivery. Participants also advised on DfP's relevance, added value, and strategies for engagement and partnership within SSA. Insight gathered from these activities guided DfP's in country engagements within SSA.

Maximising Sub-Saharan Africa's Impact in the Global Data for Policy Dialogue, DfP's inaugural convening within SSA, set the stage by examining the region's role in the global data/policy sphere. This was followed by the second convening, Advancing Data and AI Competency for Effective and Trustworthy Decision Making in Sub-Saharan Africa, which critically assessed the utilisation of AI and data science tools in the public sector. These strategic dialogues were executed in partnership with regional institutions such as the Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis (KIPPRA), and the Institute of Statistical Social and Economic Research (ISSER) at the University of Ghana. Along with amplifying regional voices and ensuring that local contexts are considered, they highlighted the need for a comprehensive approach that includes genuine knowledge exchange, capacity building, equitable investment, and the development of flexible policy frameworks tailored to the unique challenges and opportunities in SSA.

DfP's SSA programme efforts have already shown dividends. The Nairobi convening was the genesis of a conference Special Track entitled "AI, Ethics and Policy Governance in Africa". This led to SSA submissions to the Data for Policy conference increasing from 2% in 2022 to 13.45% in 2024, nearing SSA's global population share. This metric underscores the efficacy of deliberate and targeted engagement, inclusion, community building, and provision of leadership opportunities. A list of conference presentations can be found as an annex.

2. Understanding, Facilitating, and Connecting AI and Data Science Futures in Sub-Saharan Africa's Public Sector

To capitalise on the unique convening power of the Data for Policy 2024 Conference, a pre-conference working group comprising SSA researchers, practitioners, and policymakers was established. Held on 8 July at Imperial College London, the workshop provided a forum to capture DfP's engagement with SSA and present its theory of change and consortium framework for rigorous evaluation. The workshop also facilitated participants sharing their work within this domain and examining how DfP's proposed frameworks could aid in achieving their objectives. The working group was structured to encourage in-depth discussions, practical insights, and the formulation of a collaborative, forward-thinking agenda.

A series of interviews were conducted with leading figures in SSA AI and data science before the working group. Through these interviews, DfP received valuable perspectives from distinguished thought leaders such as Rachel Sibande, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, Samuel Segun, PhD, a Senior Researcher at the Global Center on AI Governance, Samuel Kobina Annim, PhD, the Government Statistician for the Ghana Statistical Service, Chukwuka Onyekwena, PhD, Executive Director at the Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa, and Lillian Olivia Orero, Founder of SafeOnline Women Kenya (SOW-Kenya). A playlist of the interview series is available on the DfP YouTube channel.

The workshop, which was rooted in the identified challenges and opportunities within SSA's AI and data science landscape, proposed several key components for discussion. These included barriers to the publication and recognition of African research, the imperative of decolonising research to elevate local knowledge, SSA's unique perspectives on the ethics of innovation, the growing significance of algorithmic governance in evidence-based policymaking, the role of private sector innovation, and the necessity for equitable investment in local initiatives. Additionally, regulatory challenges, capacity building among policymakers, and the need for adaptable policy frameworks were emphasised.

3. Workshop Discussions

The workshop commenced with introductions, showcasing the diverse expertise and perspectives of the 25 participants. Zeynep Engin, PhD, Founding Director of Data for Policy CIC, then provided an overview of DfP's growth and efforts to address programming gaps, specifically the inclusion of SSA knowledge and perspectives within the global dialogue. She highlighted the tangible progress made – evidenced by increased SSA participation in the Data for Policy 2024 Conference – and outlined future objectives, including expanding the editorial pool of the Data & Policy Journal, developing a collaborative platform for knowledge exchange coordination, and action, and planning regional conferences for 2025. Following this, participants discussed, critiqued, and provided advice on key reflections and learning from the SSA programme to date and DfP's impact map, theory of change, and consortium models, which emerged from strategic consultations held within SSA. An overview of this information is available in DfP's SSA engagement proposal.

4. Impact Map

Figure 1 Data for Policy CIC Impact Map

DfP sees its impact at the nexus of six relevant axioms of the research to policy and public service delivery pipeline. (Figure 1)

- DfP bridges the gap between advanced computation and knowledge generation and policy and practice by translating cutting-edge research into practical solutions, ensuring policy and practice inform each other in a virtuous cycle, facilitating knowledge transfer and capacity building in SSA. Equally, DfP conducts comprehensive environmental scans with needs and gaps analyses within specific contexts to inform researchers about the policy landscape, thereby aligning research efforts with the dynamic demands of the policy market.
- DfP simultaneously amplifies the global reach of SSA research and innovation by nurturing a global network for exchanging knowledge and innovation while endorsing actions that are informed by and relevant to local knowledge and contexts. This bidirectional approach not only supports local initiatives driving on-the-ground impact but also connects global expertise with local researchers and practitioners, fostering a dynamic exchange that integrates global insights with local needs and contexts.
- DfP cultivates the private sector's recognition and support of openness and collaboration by building networks that inform, engage, and persuade stakeholders to balance proprietary advancements with openness, prioritise public interest, and elevate contextually ethical and responsible development in AI and data science innovation. Additionally, DfP promotes open data initiatives and encourages collaborative partnerships between private and public sectors throughout SSA that enables the public sector to strategically leverage private sector data and expertise for improving public service delivery and governance.

DfP proposed a comprehensive approach to achieving its desired impact, emphasising several key areas. (Figure 2) The first is the importance of mission-driven exploration, translating relevant research into actionable insights that align with policy needs and timelines. This includes rigorous monitoring, evaluation and risk assessment of data-driven knowledge and socio-economic contexts to ensure innovation is both effective and contextually relevant. DfP also underscores the necessity of fostering data and technology literacy, enabling confident collaboration between researchers, innovators, and policymakers. Global partnerships and collaboration are essential, with a continued focus on building and facilitating knowledge exchange spaces.

Locally, DfP aims to identify and promote leadership, expertise, and solutions, scaling up the visibility and impact of successful projects by facilitating global exposure and links to expert networks. Furthermore, DfP envisions business models that serve the public interest and embrace social entrepreneurship by fostering innovation sandboxes with direct linkages to policy and public service delivery. Ensuring responsible innovation and regulation is paramount, with a commitment to transparency, explainability, accountability, fairness, safety, security, and legitimacy. Finally, DfP advocates for a platform that promotes effective tools and practices, provides incentives for participation, develops financial sustainability models, and fosters leadership for cultural change.

Figure 2 Data for Policy CIC Realising Impact

Participants' assessments and feedback addressed the complexities of integrating AI and data science into public policy. They highlighted issues ranging from ethics, explainability, and responsibility to meeting data governance needs in low-capacity and low-resource environments and establishing the data foundation for these initiatives. Participants also questioned how DfP will realise its impact, emphasising the need to optimise resources through strategic collaborations and strategically focus on its strengths – linking and equipping key regional and national players with readied networks and implementation capacities. Additionally, they stressed the importance of articulating and clearly differentiating DfP's roles and activities. Most importantly, participants stressed the importance of starting local when dealing in places with disparate capacities, foci, and resources.

Participants were then invited to actively engage with the framework by describing on sticky notes an immediate or direct need or problem encountered in this space. These notes were categorised under relevant axioms on a whiteboard, providing a visual and participatory critique of the framework. It also provided space for "Other" to capture important actions that DfP should consider having in its programming. This exercise not only highlighted the immediate concerns of various stakeholders but also facilitated a collaborative environment where participants could see their contributions reflected in real-time.

Advanced Computation

- Computation, cloud, compete
- Computational resources in low resource environments
- Formal versus informal LLMs
- African data sets
- African computation capacity

Within the context of Advanced Computation, participants highlighted several critical needs and/or problems whose handling are essential for the effective application of AI and data science in policy and governance. They emphasised the need for robust computational resources, including access to computation and cloud infrastructure, especially in low-resource environments. The contrast between formal and informal large language models was explored, focusing on their effective use within African contexts. The importance of developing and utilising African datasets was underscored to ensure local contexts and nuances are accurately represented. Enhancing Africa's computational capacity emerged as a key priority, with calls for increased collaboration and coordination on investment in infrastructure and training to bridge the digital divide and empower local researchers. These discussions reflect broader challenges and opportunities, highlighting the need for strategic collaborations to support AI and data science research and roles in public service delivery.

Policy & Practice

- Means and mechanisms to influence questions asked
- Explainability especially in healthcare sector
- Data solipsism versus idealism
- Incentives for change
- Digital (and data) gender divide
- Accountability

Within the context of Policy & Practice, participants identified several pivotal themes to enhance the integration of AI and data science in policy making and governance. These included the means and mechanisms necessary to influence the questions being asked, ensuring that people and policy-relevant inquiries are prioritised. The need for explainability, particularly in the healthcare sector, was emphasised to consider what trust and understanding among stakeholders would look like in different sectors. For example, we may want a simple and explainable tool when dealing with personal information. The tension between data solipsism and idealism was also highlighted, which led to a further debate on how to balance between the accuracy of data-driven insights and timeliness of information needed to meet broader societal goals. The importance of incentives to align more closely with data-driven decision-making processes was highlighted. Additionally, the digital and data gender divide was a key concern, with calls for targeted strategies to bridge this gap. Accountability in the use of data and AI emerged as a crucial aspect, ensuring that policies and practices are transparent and responsible. These discussions underscore the complexities and critical considerations of things such as transparency and responsibility in shaping policies and practices on utilising AI and data science for public benefit.

Global

- How to structure equitable (and effective) partnerships with multinational partners
- No project specifically targets youth
- AI and data conflicts
- Translation
- Regional considerations
- Legal tensions when moving from local to global (and vice versa)

Within the context of Global considerations, pressing needs and challenges directly observed in the AI and data science landscape included the difficulty in structuring equitable and effective partnerships with multinational entities to ensure fair collaboration and resource distribution. The absence of projects specifically targeting youth was noted as a significant gap, calling for initiatives that engage and empower younger demographics. Participants also discussed conflicts arising from AI and data use, emphasising the need for clear guidelines and conflict resolution mechanisms. The necessity of effective translation to bridge language and cultural barriers in global collaborations and within local service delivery was stressed. Regional considerations were brought to the forefront, underscoring the need for policies and practices that account for local nuances and contexts. Additionally, legal tensions when transitioning between local and global frameworks were highlighted, illustrating the complexities of aligning diverse legal standards and practices. These last two points particularly link with local challenges, underscoring the interplay between global strategies and regional implementations to address the unique needs and problems observed in various landscapes.

Local

- Legal ratification to domestic implementation (demonstration or effective actions)
- Defining the local knowledge discovery roadmap
- AI and the unspoken data attitude
- Youth participation for local innovation
- AI and SSA needs
- Accessibility
- Concretise needs through use cases
- Include more young minds

Within the context of Local considerations, participants identified several critical needs and challenges. They emphasised the importance of legal ratification to domestic implementation, highlighting the need for effective actions and demonstrations to ensure that policies are enacted and enforced locally. Defining a local knowledge discovery roadmap was seen as essential for guiding research and innovation tailored to specific regional contexts. The discussion also covered the unspoken attitudes towards data in the region, stressing the importance of understanding and addressing these cultural nuances. Participants highlighted the need for greater youth participation in local innovation, recognising the potential of young minds to drive forward-looking solutions. Addressing AI needs specific to SSA was deemed crucial, ensuring that AI applications are relevant and beneficial to local populations. Accessibility emerged as a key issue, with calls for making AI technologies and data resources more accessible to a broader audience. The importance of concretising needs through practical use cases was underscored to demonstrate the real-world impact of AI initiatives. Additionally, including more young minds in these processes was highlighted as vital for fostering innovation and ensuring sustainability. These discussions reflect a comprehensive approach to leveraging local strengths and addressing unique regional challenges in the AI and data science landscape.

Proprietary

- Infrastructure
- Sovereignty
- Proliferation of policies and regulations
- Synergistic agencies can combine resources to meet some of the problems
- Platform, ecosystem, franchise, standards

Within the context of Proprietary considerations, participants identified key needs and challenges, particularly in relation to the private sector and profit-driven initiatives. The necessity for robust infrastructure was emphasised, highlighting the need for adequate technological and physical resources to support AI development. Issues of sovereignty were also discussed, stressing the importance of maintaining local control over data and technological assets and processes amidst regional and global partnerships and influences. Participants noted the proliferation of policies and regulations, underscoring the complexity and potential barriers that arise from navigating multiple regulatory frameworks. They suggested that synergistic agencies could combine resources to address some of these challenges, advocating for collaborative efforts among various stakeholders. Last, participants noted the importance of developing platforms, ecosystems, franchises, and standards to create a cohesive and efficient environment for AI innovation. Follow-up discussion also touched upon the extractive and, thus, non-beneficial nature of some private sector actions. These considerations reflect the need to balance proprietary advancements and the complex and nuanced efforts required to foster innovation that benefits both the private sector – which leads this field – and public, which serves as both the source and market for their products.

Open

- Ethics and responsibility for AI democratisation
- Data education and literacy
- Plurality (norms and values)
- Collective governance and deliberation
- “Data values” (i.e., open AI is not open)
- Collaboration with the private sector is key; need to streamline governance and promote trust to facilitate meaningful collaboration

Within the context of Open considerations, participants emphasised the importance of ethics and responsibility in the democratisation of AI, ensuring that AI technologies are developed and used in a manner that benefits all stakeholders. Data education and literacy were highlighted as critical for empowering individuals and communities to effectively engage with AI technologies. The need for acknowledging and incorporating plurality, respecting diverse norms and values, was stressed to ensure locally inclusive and equitable AI development, including one that bridges the rural-urban divide. Collective governance and deliberation were seen as necessary for fostering transparent and participatory decision-making processes. Participants also discussed the concept of “data values,” pointing out that “open AI” is not truly open without these foundational principles. Collaboration with the private sector was deemed key, with a focus on streamlining governance and promoting trust to facilitate meaningful partnerships. These discussions underscored the complex interplay between and necessity of open innovation, ethical considerations, and multi-stakeholder collaboration to ensure AI advancements serve the public good.

Other

- Shallow understanding of human systems in tech
- (Lack of) locally representative data
- (Lack of reliable) electricity and related infrastructure
- Conversation on AI is still not a priority for most countries
- To be more inclusive, we have to start thinking about empowering the marginalised with the needed information
- Availability of data especially for lesser-resourced languages (LRLs)
- AI and official statistics
- Commercialisation of research
- Anticipatory governance
- Verifiable, high-quality data
- Geo-politics (China-USA)
- Cybersecurity and national sovereignty
- Computational governance – landscaping and resource constraints
- Accountable and inclusive governance
- On inclusive research, there could be research exchange programmes to foster cross-cultural collaborations
- Not only, assessing the state of things but bringing in positive change through inclusive representation from all groups
- Paucity of quantity and relevance of data/knowledge assets from under-represented communities/groups and issues is a particularly challenge in providing validity of AI uses aimed at those groups (note on local data must be key and support causal inferences)

Within the "Other" category, participants identified a wide range of pressing issues – some linking to other categories – making it the most populated section. This highlights several critical gaps and challenges in the current AI and data science landscape. Participants pointed to a shallow understanding of human systems within tech, the lack of locally representative data, and the unreliability of electricity and related infrastructure. They noted that AI conversations are not yet a priority for many countries, stressing the need to empower marginalised groups with necessary information to ensure inclusivity. The availability of data, especially for LRLs, and the integration of AI with official statistics were flagged as significant concerns. Data availability also affected the validation of AI tools for under-represented and marginalised communities and groups. The commercialisation of research, anticipatory governance, and the need for verifiable, high-quality data were also emphasised. Geo-political tensions, particularly between China and the USA, cybersecurity, and national sovereignty were identified as overarching issues affecting AI deployment. Participants stressed the importance of computational governance, landscaping, and addressing resource constraints to ensure accountable and inclusive governance. Additionally, the need for inclusive research practices was highlighted, with suggestions for research exchange programmes to foster cross-cultural collaborations. Participants advocated for not only assessing the current state but also driving positive change through inclusive representation from all groups.

The abundance of entries in this category suggests that while DfP's framework covers significant ground, there are many emerging and nuanced issues that require further attention. This indicates a need for ongoing research and dialogue to continuously adapt and expand DfP's approach to fully address the complex and evolving landscape of AI and data science. Further exploration and engagement with a broader range of stakeholders may be necessary to ensure that DfP's initiatives are comprehensive and impactful.

5. Theory of Change

Data for Policy’s theory of change is a comprehensive approach designed to address the complexities of integrating actionable insights from AI and data science research and innovation into public policy and service delivery. This multifaceted strategy includes capacity building, stakeholder engagement, and the development of robust governance frameworks. Its accompanying regional consortium framework for implementation leverages conferences and dialogues for knowledge exchange, network building, and problem-solving, a journal for knowledge dissemination, and targeted fellowships and training programmes to support leaders, change-makers and research and innovation that focus on local challenges. Additionally, it emphasises research and the development of tools and products that facilitate actionable change at the frontlines. This holistic approach ensures that complex challenges are addressed effectively and sustainably.

Our Theory of Change: SSA Focus

Inputs	Processes	Outputs	Outcomes	Impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategic talent (executive, program leadership, administration) Dedicated funds to incentivize & support SSA stakeholders for participation Dedicated funds for strategic academic partnerships to support R&D and training programs Hybrid operational infrastructure, support staff and logistics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formal regional consortium with transparent governance model Holistic DfP regional inclusion program Strategic leadership development program Systematic R&D capacity supporting community development <p>* All our processes are scalable to maximize impact at varying revenue and investment levels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proportional representation of SSA stakeholders in all DfP committee structures, authorship base, and the reviewer pool Strategic collaborations with SSA regional stakeholders, supporting them for regionally focused projects over multiple years through an open call - addressing climate change adaptation, digital economy, agricultural development, and women’s empowerment Individuals directly supported to participate in the DfP regional consortium, conferences, and journal publishing Regional policy-makers and practitioners supported through the fellowship program to develop leadership skills and capacity Research projects focused on long-term SSA engagement strategy, progress monitoring and assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of a responsive and flexible collaboration and support ecosystem that caters to stakeholders in the data for policy space at local, regional, and global levels Efficient mobilisation of resources for sustainable capacity building, aimed at facilitating the participation of underrepresented regions and maximizing the impact of regional projects Implementation of unique mission-driven leadership development models for policy-makers, addressing immediate skills shortage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bridging the gap between advanced computation and policy & practice Facilitating efficient collaboration and knowledge sharing between disciplines & sectors, and at local, regional & global scales Creating a more open, inclusive, and responsible research & innovation ecosystem Enhancing public-private sector collaborations towards addressing grand challenges (climate change adaptation, gender equality etc.)

Figure 3 Data for Policy CIC Theory of Change: SSA Focus

To realise its goals, participants tasked DfP to translate its diagnostic perspectives - such as local and global considerations - into dynamic perspectives focused on mission and change. This shift in thinking should aim for actions that drive progress toward desired outcomes. Thus, the discussion turned to leveraging the collective expertise and experience in the room to evaluate and refine the presented framework. Participants assessed how well the theory of change and consortium framework addressed needs within their sectors, nations, and regions and can “cultivate an open culture that encourages responsible innovation and fosters dynamic knowledge exchange between academia, public and private sector to effectively address complex challenges with the help of cutting-edge technologies and methods”.

Participants called for greater clarity on DfP’s actions beyond “community, conference, and journal”. They stressed DfP’s comparative advantage as its ability to integrate knowledge facilitation, knowledge translation, and capacity-building organisation specifically within the context of AI and data science for public policy and service delivery in SSA.

This means DfP can:

- Create conducive environments, tools, and practice frameworks that promote collaboration, communication, and effective use of information thereby enabling knowledge sharing, exchange, and application
- Synthesise, demonstrate application, and disseminate research and relevant knowledge to critical actors to bridge the gap between research and practice
- Provide essential guidance and critical support to critical actors, enabling them to effectively implement best practices and strategies in their frontline efforts.

All this should be done with a focus on creating practical tools and frameworks tailored to the self-identified needs within low-resource environments, particularly in SSA. Additionally, DfP's ability to act swiftly and adaptively, given its smaller size and focused mission, is a significant advantage.

As referenced prior, participants stressed the need for DfP to carefully position itself to complement existing efforts and avoid redundancy. Actions included formalising its work of establishing partnerships with leading organisations in the field to enhance its impact and visibility and leveraging its unique insights and local connections to provide nuanced, context-specific solutions that larger entities might miss or overlook. Participants also proposed tangible products such as commissioned white papers, expert rosters, and policy briefs tailored to practitioners seeking practical research translations and insight for immediate use. They provided specific recommendations to enhance the framework's impact, particularly in promoting African research and innovation. Additionally, strategies for sustained coordination, collaboration, and feedback were discussed, with an emphasis on the need for practical tools and methods to support these efforts. These recommendations focused on ensuring that DfP's initiatives are not only relevant but also actionable and impactful.

Therefore, when revising its impact map, theory of change, and consortium model, DfP should consider the following strategic points:

- Emphasise a niche in AI and data science for policy applications and public service delivery in low-resource settings, particularly in SSA
- Develop strategic partnerships with established entities like the World Bank, OECD, and UN agencies to leverage their broader networks and resources while offering DfP's specialised expertise
- Invest in developing innovative, scalable solutions that address specific local challenges as identified by regional, national, and local researchers and practitioners
- Enhance DfP's role as a thought leader by publishing not only high-impact research via the Data & Policy Journal but also policy briefs and white papers that highlight unique insights and practical applications derived from its work
- Implement robust monitoring, evaluation, and learning frameworks to demonstrate impact and attract future investment, partners, and participants.

6. Looking to the Future

While DfP's proposed activities were not entirely unique, participants saw a critical need for thoughtful work in the field that is focused on specific regional and contextual challenges, fostering strategic partnerships, and driving innovation in practical applications of AI and data science in public policy. To that end, participants shared their initiatives – discussing their status, opportunities, challenges, and gaps – that can directly benefit from such an organisation. This exercise facilitated a deeper understanding of how individual initiatives could align with and enhance the broader framework.

There were a variety of immediate and near-future work initiatives, focusing on practical applications of AI, data science, and policy research to solve pressing local and global issues across diverse contexts. A recurring theme is the application of AI to predict and analyse economic and social phenomena. For instance, one participant is working on predicting the success of retail agent businesses in Ghana, with implications for employment, financial inclusion, and market sustainability. This study, while locally focused, is expected to have significant global relevance, although alternative dissemination methods beyond traditional publishing may be necessary due to potential publication challenges. The versatility in AI research and applications is seen in its use in predicting coup d'états, credit ratings with a focus on potential African biases, and the success of mobile money agents. Efforts to improve data management and integration were also seen in projects creating an online repository of data statistics and policies, using large language models to identify disconnects and enhance data architecture, and developing generative AI methods to analyse the influence of policies and laws from diverse sources, including social and conservative media, markets, courts, and emerging social movements.

Another area of work is the development of community-based solutions to bridge the digital divide and enhance digital literacy. SafeOnline Women Kenya is pioneering efforts to counter cyberbullying through a mobile app, "Safetter," and is providing digital literacy training for marginalised young women and girls, with an emphasis on local language accessibility. The Center for Human-Inspired AI at the University of Cambridge was also highlighted with its work dedicated to leveraging existing resources to foster innovation. It builds local capacities of local AI innovators by collaborating with young researchers from underserved communities. Additionally, international initiatives such as the Global Artificial Intelligence for Pandemic and Epidemic Preparedness and Response Network also emphasise the need for international cooperation in leveraging AI for development and crisis response, particularly in pandemic and epidemic preparedness. Additionally, the Africa-Canada Artificial Intelligence Unit Data Innovation Consortium shows the growing cadre of collaborative effort to drive innovation across continents.

In the realm of governance, several projects focus on normative AI governance, ethics, and bias, as well as compute governance in low-resource environments. These initiatives aim to establish ethical standards, ensure fair resource allocation, and promote democratic deliberation in AI deployment. Research on the ethical use of personalised algorithms in the digital economy is being conducted by the Ikiga Innovation Initiative. It examines the impact of algorithmic pricing on users and explores data protection laws and AI regulations. It also involves conducting workshops for the private sector on ethical data use and raising awareness about regulatory responses to discriminatory practices in personalised pricing.

Several strategic and multi-faceted projects aimed at addressing education, governance, collaboration, and ethical considerations in the SSA context were mentioned. One critical recommendation is to close the AI educational gap in SSA. This involves creating targeted educational programmes that integrate AI literacy and skills into the curriculum at all levels,

from primary education to higher education. This approach is essential to equip the region's workforce with the necessary skills to harness AI's potential effectively. By addressing the educational disparity, we can ensure a more inclusive and equitable adoption of AI technologies, fostering innovation and economic growth in the region.

Another major focus is on establishing context-based data governance frameworks and advocacy. This includes developing legal frameworks that ensure the enforceability and domestication of data policies, aligning them with local contexts and needs. The emphasis is on creating adaptable and resilient governance structures that can anticipate and respond to future challenges, a concept known as anticipatory governance. Additionally, strengthening supranational organisations in the region is crucial to promote collaboration and unified standards across countries, thereby enhancing regional stability and growth. Clarifying the meaning of "responsible" in AI development and governance, and building foundational blocks for ethical AI practices, are also vital steps towards creating a sustainable and trustworthy AI ecosystem. The recommendations also highlight the importance of clustering normative and social simulations and identifying stakeholder tensions. This involves using advanced social simulations to understand the dynamics between various stakeholders and predict potential conflicts, enabling more informed decision-making and policy development.

The working group concluded with a discussion on placing current initiatives within the DfP framework and identifying collaboration points where DfP could add significant value. Participants reflected on whether the framework prioritised and addressed the initiatives they highlighted and, if not, how it could be revised to better align with their work. The discussion also outlined roles and opportunities within the DfP framework, including area editors for the Data & Policy Journal and regional committee members and planned initiatives, regional conferences, and partnership opportunities were also discussed with involvement and participation encouraged.

7. Conclusion

This strategic working group successfully achieved its objectives by engaging SSA and project partners in a dialogue and critical assessments of DfP's frameworks and strategies. Participants provided valuable feedback on DfP's theory of change and consortium framework and emphasised the importance of niche, actionable insights, effective resource and network utilisation, and strategic collaborations. The workshop highlighted DfP's role as a facilitator of knowledge and innovation, particularly within the SSA context, and underscored the need for clarity in DfP's initiatives beyond its current scope. The session also fostered commitments to roles such as area editors, regional committee members, and partners for future proposals and conferences, confirming ongoing engagement and collaboration.

To capitalise on the feedback received, DfP will refine its frameworks to distinguish its work, add needed linkage services, address specific local challenges, promote SSA research and innovation, and enhance global partnerships. A focus on capacity-building initiatives and creating tailored tools and frameworks for low-resource environments will be crucial. Additionally, DfP will formalise partnerships with leading organisations to leverage broader networks and resources and increase the market for its specialised expertise. Equally as important, DfP will embark on building a more rigorous monitoring, evaluation and learning (MEL) process to demonstrate its impact, attract investment, and ensure that initiatives are both relevant and actionable.

DfP looks forward to working closely with local and regional thought leaders and innovators and helping them drive SSA advancements in AI and data science for public policy and service delivery.

8. Annex

Strategic Consultation Agenda

Understanding, Facilitating, and Connecting AI and Data Science Futures in Sub-Saharan Africa's Public Sector

Monday, 8 July 2024, 15:00 – 17:00 | Data Science Institute Boardroom, Imperial College

Participant Arrivals

15:00 Coffee/Tea

15:10 Welcome & Introductions

Zeynep Engin, PhD

Founding Director | Data for Policy CIC

Editor in Chief | Data & Policy, Cambridge University Press

Rachel Sibande, PhD

Senior Officer, Global Development | Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

Mark Kennedy, PhD

Director, Data Science Institute | Imperial College London

Insights & Learnings

15:20 Data for Policy CIC – SSA Engagement

- Key reflections and learning on successful engagement strategies, outcomes, and lessons learned
- Present theory of change and consortium framework for addressing capacity, coordination, participatory and inclusive engagement, cross-sector collaboration, and supporting research and development of data governance and regulatory frameworks
- Show how structure supports current and future objectives and activities such as expanding Data & Policy Journal editor pool, 2025 regional conferences, and regional and subject area committees

Diasmer Panna Bloe

Researcher | Data for Policy CIC

15:35 Discussion: Framework for Action

- Leveraging your expertise and experience, how well does our theory of change and consortium framework address the needs within your sector, nation, and/or region?
 - What specific recommendations can you offer to improve, refine, and amplify the impact of our framework, particularly in enhancing your needs and the visibility, recognition, and use of locally generated African research and innovation?
- What strategies or approaches can ensure sustained, strong coordination, collaboration and feedback moving forward? Are there particular tools or methods you would recommend?

16:00 Break

Collaborative & Strategic Action

16:05 Current Efforts for Future Collaboration

Present your current public sector data science and AI initiatives that fall along DFP axioms:

- Bridging the gap between advanced computational and technological research and policy and practice, ensuring research is not only understood but its insights are effectively applied for tangible public benefit

- Merging global platforms for collaboration and sharing research, findings, and systems with local knowledge generation, innovation, and impact
 - Harmonising private sector's proprietary and frontier dynamics with open, responsible innovation aimed at public benefit
- Share status, opportunities, challenges, and missing elements or gaps

16:30 Discussion: Framework in Action

- Does DFP's framework prioritise, reflect, and/or address your initiatives? If not, how can it do so?
- Can we place your initiatives within the framework? If so, where?
- Given your current and upcoming initiatives, how can DFP's consortium framework align with and enhance your work?
- Identify collaboration points where DFP can add significant value and define the roles and function of DFP given its current theory of change and consortium framework.

16:50 Broader Strategy for Consolidating Regional and International Efforts

Roles available: Area editors (D&P), regional committee members Opportunities:

Regional conferences, partnerships for pursuing funding opportunities, other collaborative initiatives

17:00 Closing & Adjourn

Group Photo
Interviews

Participant Organisations at the Stakeholder Consultation

Africa-Canada AI & Data Innovation Consortium, Canada
Akademiya 2063, Senegal
Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa, Nigeria
Data For Policy CIC, UK
Equiano Institute, South Africa
Gates Foundation, USA
Ghana Statistical Service, Ghana
Global Center on AI Governance, South Africa
African Observatory on Responsible AI, South Africa
Imperial College London, UK
Interdisciplinary Network for Technology and Entrepreneurship Research in Africa
Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research and Analysis, Kenya
Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, Kenya
Kera Health Platforms, Senegal
Microsoft, USA
National Research Council of Canada, Canada
SafeOnline Women Kenya (SOW-Kenya), Kenya
The Computer Lab, University of Cambridge, UK
The GovLab, New York University, USA
UNICEF, USA
University of Ghana Business School, Ghana
University of Ottawa, Canada
University of Washington, USA
Veeta Advisory Hub, Rwanda
SSA-linked Presentations at Data for Policy 2024

Authors	Presentation title	Country
Eric Afful-Dadzie and Samuel Larrey	Knowledge, Attitudes and Readiness Towards Artificial Intelligence in Government Services; A developing Country Perspective	Ghana
Dorcas Nyamwaya, Susan Otieno, Chinasa T. Okolo, Abigail Oppong and Jonas Kgomo	Towards A Fair and Equitable Data Ecosystem for Low Resource Languages	Kenya, USA, Ghana, South Africa
Jonas Kgomo	Community Based AI Governance	South Africa
Amara Esther Chimakonam	The Ethics at the Intersection of Artificial Intelligence and Transhumanism: A Personhood-Based Approach	South Africa
Paul Plantinga, Kristophina Shilongo, Oarabile Mudongo, Angelique Umubyeyi and Gabriella Razzano	Responsible artificial intelligence in Africa: Towards policy learning	South Africa
Connor Wright	Should we communicate with the dead to assuage our grief? An Ubuntu perspective on governing griefbots	UK
Samuel Segun	Are Certain African Ethical Values at Risk from Artificial Intelligence?	South Africa
Abiola Joseph Azeez and Tosin Adeate	Trust Norms for Generative AI Data Gathering in the African Context	Canada, Nigeria
Aishat Oyenike Salami	Artificial Intelligence, Digital Colonialism and the Implications for Africa's Future Development	Nigeria
Kadijatou Diallo, Jonathan Smith, Chinasa T. Okolo, Dorcas Nyamwaya, Jonas Kgomo and Richard Ngamita	Case Studies of AI Policy Development in Africa	USA, Kenya
Getachew Hailemariam Mengesha and Elefelious Getachew Belay	Social Justice Considerations in Developing and Deploying AI in Africa	Ethiopia
Tracey Li, Abbas Wandella, Richard Gomer and Mohamed Habib Al-Mafazy	Operationalizing health data governance for AI innovation in low-resource government health systems - a practical implementation perspective	United Republic of Tanzania, UK
Omotubora, Adekemi Olufunmilola	AI for Women's Financial Inclusion– An Analysis of Product Design and Policy Approaches in Nigeria	Nigeria
Daniel Osarfo, Peter Quartey, Agyapomaa Gyeke-Dako and Elikplimi K Agbloyor	Predicting the Entry, Success and Exit of Mobile Money Retail Agents in Ghana using Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning	Ghana
Lilian Olivia Orero	Fair AI for All: Gender Equity in Decision-Making Algorithms in Sub-Saharan Africa	Kenya
Elikplimi K Agbloyor, Boakye Danquah, Agyapomaa Gyeke Dako and Lei Pan	The 'Coup' Season: What Can Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence Tell Us About the Resurgence of Coup D'Etats in Africa?	Ghana

Thank You

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